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Partisan Differences in Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions

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Research Question

- Do US partisan voters differ in punitiveness in response to politicians' moral violations and whether these differences persist when controlling for voters' perceptions of severity of moral violations.

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Hypotheses

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- **Partisanship Hypothesis (H1):** Republicans have a stronger desire to punish politicians' involved in moral transgressions than Democrats
- **In party Bias Hypothesis (H2):** Voters have a stronger desire to punish outgroup politicians involved in moral transgressions than ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions
- **Perceived Severity Hypothesis (H3):** The more morally wrong voters perceive the politician's moral transgression the stronger their desire for punishment of the transgressing politician.

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Experimental Design

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- A vignette study using a between-subjects experiment in a 6 x 3 design embedded in a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 3000 U.S. voters
- We manipulated the moral principle violated (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity) and added a social norm violation as a baseline
- We manipulated the partisanship of the politician (Republican, Democrat, no partisanship) in the vignette
- Each respondent was randomly assigned a short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic sounding, scenario
- Data were collected between 2 October 2020 and 3 November 2020 by Dynata
- We restrict analyses to 2074 partisan voters exposed to a moral violation

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Stimulus Material

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Norm violated	Vignette (non-partisan)
Care	You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.
Fairness	You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Loyalty	You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.
Authority	You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.
Sanctity	You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.
Social	You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

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Punitiveness Scale

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Individual Items							
	Labels	RC	Mean	Standard Deviation	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.7106	1.4331	.7614	80.9204	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.6831	1.4405	.7580	80.8318	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.5816	1.3932	.7177	76.5392	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.0966	1.5555	.6864	72.4233	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.3820	1.4859	.6504	69.2458	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.2162	1.5625	.7010	74.6550	Y
Scale							
	Punitiveness, i.e. the desire to punish		Mean	Standard Deviation	H	Z	
			20.6702	7.6023	.7118	131.0212	

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The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness

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The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Perceived Severity

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In-party Bias of Democrats and Republicans' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Severity

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Conclusions

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- Democrats show higher levels of punitiveness than Republicans for moral transgressions perceived moderate and high in severity, only Republicans show in-party bias for moral transgression perceived low in severity
- Other recent research supports these unexpected partisan differences (Morais, Abrams & Randsley de Moura, 2020; Howard, Cervone & Motyl, 2022).
- Not only do the results show partisan voters' heterogeneity in punitiveness, but also that this relationship is strongly mediated by perceived severity.

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